

LAMB WAVES GENERATION USING A TRANSDUCER EMBEDDED IN A COMPOSITE PLATE

Emmanuel Moulin¹, Jamal Assaad¹, Christophe Delebarre¹ and Daniel Osmont²

¹ *IEMN, UMR CNRS 9929, OAE Department, Université de Valenciennes et du Hainaut Cambrésis, le Mont Houy, BP 311, 59304 - Valenciennes Cedex, France.*

² *ONERA, Solid Mechanics and Damage Department, BP 72, 92322 – Chatillon Cedex, France.*

SUMMARY : Integrated Health Monitoring of composite structures could be performed using Lamb waves generated by miniaturised piezoelectric transducers, intimately coupled to the materials. Therefore, in order to verify the practical feasibility and assess the performances of such a system, a specimen has been built. It consists of a carbon-epoxy composite plate containing a thin embedded piezoelectric element. A general experimental evaluation of this specimen has been conducted. In addition to a post-manufacturing check-up using non destructive testing techniques, the ability of generating efficient Lamb waves has been verified. A precise characterisation of the surface displacement field has also been enabled by using optical measurement techniques. Moreover, an original model of the considered specimen is presented and the obtained results are successfully compared to the experimental ones. The aim of the development of this modelling method is to get the ability of optimising the system, avoiding systematic experimentation.

KEYWORDS: Health Monitoring, Lamb Waves, Normal Modes, Finite Element, Piezoelectric Transducer, Nondestructive Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

As part of the concept of “smart materials”, the idea of “sensitive materials” has been receiving a great deal of attention for a few years. The aim is to design structures components able to perform their own health monitoring. Since they interact with defects in plates and can propagate over long distances, Lamb waves appear to be one of the most promising techniques. The usual way of generating Lamb waves [1] (excitation by longitudinal waves under oblique incidence) allows a proper control of the excited modes. However this technique, which requires the use of quite bulky wedge transducers or underwater excitation, clearly appears to be inadequate for sensitive materials applications.

Therefore the use of thin piezoelectric elements integrated to the structure is investigated. The main problems to be solved for this kind of systems are : firstly, the feasibility of manufacturing them ; secondly, their ability to efficiently generate Lamb waves ; and thirdly, the possibility to control the excited modes. This work aims at contributing answer these fundamental questions. An experimental specimen is presented, consisting of a piece of composite plate containing a thin piezoelectric transducer embedded into its thickness. First of all the specimen has been non-destructively controlled, in order to check the suitability of the used manufacturing technique to elaborate such systems. Then the generation of Lamb waves using the embedded transducer has been characterised. At last, a theoretical modelling technique of the system is presented.

DESCRIPTION OF THE SPECIMEN

A thin parallelepiped-shaped piezoelectric transducer is embedded inside a 4 mm thick plate. This composite plate consists in 32 unidirectional carbon-epoxy plies. The piezoelectric insert is a 350 μm thick and 1 cm sided PZ-27 ceramic. It has been inserted, during the manufacturing process, between the two central plies. The electric connection to the outside of the plate is enabled by two metallized 25 μm thick Kapton film, bonded to the ceramic transducer. Thus the total thickness of the insert is 400 μm . Fig. 1 (transverse cut and top-view) schematically presents the configuration of the considered specimen.

Fig. 1 : Specimen configuration

NON DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF THE INSERT

A ultrasound control of the embedded transducer and its close vicinity has been performed. The aim is to verify that no critical damage of the insert has occurred during the polymerisation process of the composite plate. Indeed, the plate is submitted to pressure and temperature cycles which could be dangerous for the piezoelectric element.

This non destructive testing (Fig. 2) consists in measuring the signal time of flight in pulse-echo mode (D-scan), using a focused transducer at 25 MHz. This technique enables to estimate the location of the insert within the plate thickness.

Fig. 2 : D-scan of the insert area

As a result, the integrity of the embedded transducer seems to have been preserved. The two lateral strips visible in the rear side view (Fig. 2-b) are probably due to the slope of Kapton film at both sides.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to determine the working frequency ranges, the frequency response of the system has been measured. The embedded transducer has been excited by a short electric pulse and the Fourier transform of the signal received by a wedge transducer at a distance of 30 cm has been displayed (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 : Frequency response

Different frequency ranges at which Lamb waves generation appear to be efficient are evident from this graph. Compared to the signals obtained by emitting with a classical wedge transducer, the received signal amplitudes have proved to be of the same order, or even slightly higher.

As an example, the following graph presents the signal received by the wedge transducer (**Erreur! Source du renvoi introuvable.**-b), when the embedded transducer is excited by a 5 cycles sinusoid toneburst of 330 kHz frequency (corresponding to one of the peaks) and 10 V amplitude.

Fig. 4 : Acquired signal at 330 kHz (a-emission ; b-reception)

Since their propagation velocities are well distinct at this frequency, the S_0 and A_0 modes are clearly distinguishable. However, S_0 appears to be much more efficiently excited. In addition, the higher surface normal displacement for S_0 mode is theoretically obtained at this frequency for the considered type of plate. Therefore, the best results from the shearography are likely to be obtained at 330 kHz.

Shearography [2] (or phase-shifting speckle interferometry) is an optical measurement technique, which enables to visualise very small normal surface displacements (typically of the order of nanometers). Its principle is based on interference between two spatially shifted images of a same object. To obtain the phase image of the object (which is related to the object's shape), the phase-shifting technique [3] is used. This technique requires the acquisition of four correlation fringes images with shifted phases, to build one phase image. Thus the difference between two phase images obtained for two different states of the object, gives a representation of the object deformations between the two states.

In the case of harmonic Lamb waves excitation, best results are obtained by setting the spatial shift d_x to be the half-wavelength of the considered Lamb wave [2]. The first and second states consist in stroboscopic the incident laser in phase and in opposite phase respectively with the excitation signal, so that the largest deformation occurs between the two states. After unwrapping the phase values, the difference of these two phase images can be directly correlated to the normal surface displacement values.

Thus the following images (Fig. 4) are a visualisation of the normal surface displacement in the plate submitted to Lamb waves propagation at 330 kHz.

Fig. 4 : Shearography imaging at 330 kHz

In the first view (Fig. 4-a), \mathbf{d}_x is set to the half-wavelength of S_0 , whereas in the second view (Fig. 4-b), it is set to the half-wavelength of A_0 . So these two Lamb waves appear to be simultaneously present in the plate, though S_0 proves again to be more efficiently generated. The effect of the plate's high anisotropy on the propagation of S_0 is clearly visible (elliptic wavefronts). The propagation energy seems to especially concentrate along the fibre axis, which suggests the hypothesis (used in the model) of a quasi-unidirectional propagation.

THE MODELING METHOD

The model presented here is based on the Normal Modes Expansion method (extensively presented by B. A. Auld [4]). Its basic principle is to consider the acoustic field in a waveguide as a linear combination of its eigenmodes (the Lamb waves, in the case of a plate) :

$$\mathbf{t}(x, z) = \sum_n a_n(x) \mathbf{t}_n(z) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{t}_n = \begin{pmatrix} v_{nx} \\ v_{nz} \\ \mathbf{s}_{nxx} \\ \mathbf{s}_{nxz} \end{pmatrix}$ is the acoustic field vector for the n^{th} Lamb mode.

(\mathbf{v}_n is the particle velocity vector and \mathbf{s}_{nx} is the stress vector according to the plate section).

If the mechanical field related to each normal mode is assumed to be known, then the problem is to evaluate the different mode amplitudes as a function of the excitation configuration. This can be performed by projecting the local mechanical field in the eigenmode basis.

The case of the piezoelectric transducer embedded into a composite plate is considered (Fig. 5) :

Fig. 5 : Modelled configuration

$\mathbf{t}_0(z) = \mathbf{t}(L_0, z)$ is defined to be the acoustic field in a section located at a distance (L_0-L) from the transducer edge. Then the amplitude a_m of the m^{th} mode can be expressed as a function of the components of $\mathbf{t}_0(z)$:

$$a_m(x) = -\frac{e^{jk_m(L_0-x)}}{4P_{mm}} \int_{-d}^d (v_{0x} \mathbf{S}_{mxx}^* + v_{0z} \mathbf{S}_{mzx}^* + v_{mx}^* \mathbf{S}_{0xx} + v_{mz}^* \mathbf{S}_{0zx}) dz \quad (2)$$

Since in the present case, the mechanical excitation given by the piezoelectric insert is unknown, the local acoustic field \mathbf{t}_0 is numerically computed, using the finite element method. In order to simulate an infinite structure with a limited finite element mesh, absorbing conditions are imposed at the mesh boundary. In this way, the used finite element modelling can be reduced to the transducer and its close vicinity [5].

This method has been applied to the above presented specimen. Recombination of the individual mode contributions gives the global acoustic field in the plate. In this way, the normal displacement at the upper surface has been determined. The comparison with the normal displacement profile extracted from the shearography imaging at 330 kHz (Fig. 4-a) is shown below (Fig. 6) :

Fig. 6 : Comparison between theoretical and experimental normal displacements (330 kHz)

A relatively good agreement is obtained between the experimental and theoretical curves. Though complementary studies would be necessary to precisely determine the involved parameters, it seems likely that the slight discrepancies could be explained whether by model assumptions (unidirectional propagation and no losses taken into account, for instance) or by experimental uncertainties (such as the quality of the plate / transducer interface, or inaccuracy on so small displacement values).

CONCLUSION

This work was based on the study of a composite plate integrating a thin embedded piezoelectric transducer. This specimen represents a preliminary step towards the development of sensitive materials. First, the manufacturing process of the composite plate has proved to be compatible with the insertion of a piezoelectric element. Good experimental properties as regards the generation of Lamb waves have also been demonstrated. In addition, the promising results obtained using the presented model let hope the possibility of optimising the behaviour of systems of this type, without exhaustive experimentation.

REFERENCES

1. I. A. Viktorov, *Rayleigh and Lamb waves*, Plenum Press, New York, 1967.
2. T. Lamarque, 'Caractérisation de délaminages par interférométrie de speckle à cisaillement avec sollicitation thermique ou mécanique', *Thèse de doctorat*, Université Paris 6, mars 1998.
3. K. Creath, 'Phase -shifting speckle interferometry', *Applied Optics*, vol. 24, pp. 3053-3058.
4. B. A. Auld, *Acoustic Fields and Waves in Solids*, Vol. II, 2nd ed., Krieger Fl., 1990.
5. E. Moulin *et al.*, 'Modelling of Lamb waves generated by integrated transducers in composite plates, using a coupled Finite Element - Normal Modes Expansion method', *Submitted for publication to J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*